

D5.2 Best practices recommendation from UZH and TUM

Name of project: **Fostering high scientific quality in protein research in Eastern
Slovakia (CasProt)**

No. 952333

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Leader/Coordinator of the project CasProt – Pavol Jozef Šafárik University in Košice (UPJS) formulated the following recommendations and best practices divided to several chapters such as project preparation, project management and financial management using the body of evidence established via the two on-job trainings of administrative staff which took place at two partner universities - Technical University in Munich (TUM) and University of Zurich (UZH).

As the creating of project teams and legal frameworks based on national specificities are different in the regions of Germany, Switzerland and Slovakia, some of the good practices are not possible to apply, but UPJS team will give its best efforts to apply as much as possible.

Without good research content, the administration is not able to strengthen the help, so the motivation should come especially from researchers - Having a great content is essential. Projects must fit into broader strategies, so overall university cooperation and good processes are necessary for improving project funding finding. The university should provide multilateral support to young researchers and create good conditions to develop their skills and transform their ideas into business ideas that should bring overall social benefits. Inspired by partner universities' departments, people from UPJS project support will do their best to provide focused professional and personalized assistance.

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Chapter 1. General information about partners' universities

Technical University in Munich (TUM) - Physics Department

<https://www.biophysics-tum.de/>

The main research of the Physics Department of TUM is to study a quantitative understanding of biological processes which is also one of the main objectives of biophysics. Especially, at the Institute of molecular and cellular biophysics, they join efforts to unravel the fundamental mechanisms underlying such processes with interdisciplinary approaches.

The TUM has an office for project support. **Office for Research and Innovation (TUM ForTe)** is the first point of contact and the central coordinating body for any form of cooperation between the business and research sectors, research funding support, and technology transfer at TUM. Team for cooperation between the business and research sectors provides assistance to scientists and scholars at TUM in gearing their research projects with outside research or business partners toward the university's strategic development goals. It also acts as a point of contact between scientists and scholars at TUM, businesses, universities and non-university research facilities.

Fig. 1 Organization structure of ForTe TUM

University of Zurich (UZH) - Department of Biochemistry

<https://www.bioc.uzh.ch/en.html>

The Department of Biochemistry is committed to cutting-edge research and to offering an outstanding biochemistry curriculum compliant with international standards. Their laboratories are located at the Irchel Campus in Zurich.

Their research is focused on the functional investigation of biomolecular mechanisms using biophysical, biochemical, and structural approaches. Currently, the department hosts six research groups and houses excellent infrastructure for biomolecular research. Thanks to the development of new technologies and the subsequent acquisition of patents relevant for biomedical applications, several spin-off companies have evolved from the department.

There are several departments related to grants/project support:

1. EU National Grants Grant Access;
2. Drittmittelmanagement an der UZH;
3. Separate support teams for each research leader.

EU GrantsAccess is a joint office of the University of Zurich and ETH Zurich. At ETH Zurich, EU GrantsAccess forms part of the [Office of the Vice President for Research](#); at the University of Zurich, EU GrantsAccess is a division of the [external page Office of the Vice President Research](#)

EU GrantAccess is the competence centre for international research programs. It is a joint office of the University of Zurich and ETH Zurich since 1997 and provides support for all international grants during the project lifecycle.

Services and support for faculty and staff:

Pre- and post-award support for all international research programmes: EU Framework Programmes, COST, US Grants (NIH, NSF and others), Eurostarsetc.

- Advice about funding opportunities also for young scientists.
- Idea checking and proposal pre-screening.
- Administrative, financial and legal support.
- Proposal writing workshops – tips how to write formally, not from research view.
- Individual coaching.
- Information events.
- Publication of Science Stories.
- Project management of selected ETH and UZH FP projects.

Drittmittelmanagement an der UZH

- Third-party funds have become indispensable at UZH. These project contributions are very important for UZH.
- If the basic funding stagnates or even decreases, the acquisition of third-party funds becomes more and more important.
- The acquisition of third-party funds by researchers makes an important contribution to the excellent position of UZH. Since new findings from third-party funded research projects

are systematically incorporated into teaching flow into it, teaching ultimately benefits directly from it, among other things.

- The end-to-end third-party funding process starts with raising funds and ends with reporting to the donor.
- In the third-party funds administration, however, there are fields to be edited in order to improve efficiency in processing from third-party funds.
- Contact point for information in connection with the financial processing of third-party funded projects.
- Advice and support for the project owners for financial questions and mediation of funder requirements.
- Contract assessment and opening in the system.
- Management of ongoing third-party funded projects.
- Reporting/reporting (interim/final reports).
- Monitoring and organization of audits.

Chapter 2. Project preparation, Project dissemination, communications, exploitations

Recommendation 1: Related to new calls – provide **nonstop information campaigns/services out the team's possibility of funding within the whole universities research teams** (including senior researchers - professors, associated professors, young researchers, PhD students).

The means of information campaigns UPJS team gets from good practices of TUM and ZUH:

- ✓ periodical newsletters,
- ✓ database with open calls accessible on the website,
- ✓ sub-website specialised for researchers and innovators (UZH innovation),
- ✓ consulting/online consulting, seminars, webinars,
- ✓ face2face meetings with researchers,
- ✓ social media campaigns,
- ✓ students and young researcher's community should be involved in (e.g. storytelling).

Another means how to involve more researchers to project preparation is a personalized way of forming them about new calls via email with specific calls which means to have from them exact descriptions of their research work. There should prepare a database with university research teams and their précised research focus.

UPJS Team got inspired on:

- a Grant access website (<https://grantsaccess.ethz.ch/>) and social media (LinkedIn, Twitter).
- They have their own call database:

1st website for TRL 1-6: <https://www.research.uzh.ch/de.html>;

2nd website for TRL 7-9 (innovation): <https://www.innovation.uzh.ch/de.html>;

- 2 websites: information campaign about successful projects and researchers involved in it between researchers - **Science stories** (<https://science-stories.ch/>), the main idea is to make successful project more visible
- **Newsletter**: we strongly recommend preparing newsletters with new calls for each faculty at least on a bimonthly basis.

Recommendation 2: Paid platforms for finding of funding.

UZH pays membership fees for two licensed platforms: **CrowdHelix** and **researchprofessional.com**

One of the servers is **CrowdHelix**, which is an Open Innovation platform that forges links between an international network of excellent researchers and innovating companies, so that they can plan and deliver pioneering collaborative projects.

They strongly recommend paying similar partner search platforms.

TUM find partners based on own experiences and existing contacts (from previous project cooperation)

TUM also has its own search engines, not only through the Funding and Tenders page. For example: Home | Research Funding – Technical University of Munich (TUM) (open4research.eu) where you need to be registered.

Therefore, we should find a suitable platform, in the first phase and we should consider the head of the university to pay for such a platform and give it as part of the expenditure part, in the second step. The same should be done for ESFRI infrastructures and European partnerships of the Horizon Europe program and international small alliances.

Recommendation 3: Good time management.

I. Overall recommendation is to start writing proposals: To start preparing/ writing the proposal in advance (approx. 6 months before the opening of the call) and ask the NCP for the pre-screening of the proposal 3 months before the deadline.

II. Overall recommendation to push local NCP to move the working versions of the Work programs to us, so that we can comment on them, and we could start working in advance on the project proposals - like they do in Switzerland. Because is too late to start writing proposals on the date of official publish of the Work program.

We suggest preparing a letter for CVTI signed by the rector and ask them to make the work programs available more in advance (also in working versions).

Recommendation 4: Proposal to write a joint MSCA project between UPJS, UZH and Ukraine.

In connection with the war situation in Ukraine, UZH suggests that we write a joint MSCA project to support students from Ukraine or create a joint study program. This means that part of the study would take place in Zurich and part in Košice in the field of biomedical sciences.

Recommendation 5: Proposals made based on personal international research cooperation and local industry engagement.

The effort to establish connections from the scientific sphere to a greater extent than before, also for the purpose of creating successful consortia. The researchers from ZUH and TUM recommend paying more attention to finding personal contacts for proposal preparation and consortia creation. Only after proper and deep evaluation research subject could be prepared a valuable sense-making proposal.

Recommendation 6: Unification of project submission processes.

At both universities each proposal must be approved at the university management level. Before providing to the university management the proposal must be registered at the university project support office. This will prevent the submission of projects with the same focus. The university management confirms the eligibility to implement the project based on material and personal capacities.

Recommendation 7: Budget preparation.

Budget is prepared based on previous performances. For UPJS it would mean to invite to prepared project young researchers with higher salaries, so they would be more inspired to stay in academia, even for a shorter time during the project. Now, they leave academia also because of low salaries.

Chapter 3. Project implementation - Administrative, financial and legal issues, Public procurement

Recommendation 1: Consider the change of internal structure of Project Support Department.

At EU GrantAccess have better Internal Organisation structure – Knowledge – they are divided into the different subteams and have regular meeting:

- Daily “Meet the Experts” (MEX);
- Weekly meetings within subteams;
- Weekly Board Meetings;
- Biweekly Coordination Board Meetings;
- Monthly: knowledge exchange meetings;
- They have common email address followed with by redistribution of work.

We recommend redistribution competencies clearly at the international project department at UPJS and have regular meetings or the purpose of mutual information and coordination. The system as the competences are divided at the project support departments described at the beginning of this document will be inseparable part of future negotiations regarding work distribution at UPJS project support department.

Fig.2 Inspiration how to improve the project department

Recommendation 2: Each project has two project managers – one for *scientific* content and one for *administrative* issues. It is easier for whole procedure of the project: providing deliverables and milestones for scientific part and also for coordination par. Every professor as team leader has its own administrative support and the responsibility for worked done on proposals and on implementation is more on research personal as on administrative staff.

Recommendation 3: Financial issues.

After a project is successful, UZH partner has a separate external department **Drittmittelmanagement** - who overtakes financial issues over the whole international projects - that checks financial reports and at the same time an externally ordered audit company that checks each spending.

The roles are strictly given based on the specific work. This is also connected with the more specific work distributed between separate university departments (finance office, travel expenses office, personal office).

Recommendation 4: Legal issues.

Preparation of agreements - strictly follows EU templates / conditions GA a CA.

Remark: our system is basically the same.

Recommendation 5: Best value for money.

Public procurement - Reconsider / Adjust internal directions which regulates public procurement in less bureaucracy and administrative way. Coordinate it with the legal department.

Simplification of the process, as EU law regulates only orders below and above the limit, but not orders with a low value.

UZH have their internal system for Public Procurement - they have contracted standard suppliers and an order system called Purchase for you – “Pforyou”, through which they order equipment, chemicals etc.

Q: Do you need to provide 3 offers for each order or only for the order for a particular sum? A: No.

At partner universities, orders are not subject to public procurement, if it is:

- TUM – more than 5,000€
- UZH – more than 10,000€

Best quality decides – it's not the price that matters, but the quality.

Recommendation 6: Public procurement - New in ZVO - orders related to science and research is subject to an exception.

The task needs to be submitted to university financial management how to deal with it and make easier procurement for the researchers.